

VARIOUS EXAMPLES OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION IN THE CLASSROOM, ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION

Nematova Zebo Tursunboevna

ESP teacher at Bukhara State Medical Institute named after

Abu Ali ibn Sino Bukhara, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7439835>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st November 2022

Accepted: 10th November 2022

Online: 12th November 2022

KEY WORDS

Differentiated learning, interactive method, advanced, PowerPoint presentations, educational, formative assessments, summative assessments, content, kinesthetic learners, product, learning environment.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is using differentiated instruction in the classroom. This article will first explain the definition of differentiated instruction, history of differentiated instruction, list four ways of differentiated instruction. Then it will illustrate the pros and cons of differentiated instruction.

Introduction. Just as everyone has a unique fingerprint, every student has an individual learning style. Chances are, not all of your students grasp a subject in the same way or share the same level of ability. So how can you better deliver your lessons to reach *everyone* in class? Consider differentiated instruction—a method you may have heard about but have not explored. In this article, learn exactly what it means, how it works, and the pros and cons.

Definition of differentiated instruction

[Carol Ann Tomlinson](#) is a leader in the area of differentiated learning and professor of educational leadership, foundations, and policy at the University of Virginia. Tomlinson describes differentiated instruction as factoring students' individual learning styles and levels of readiness

first *before* designing a lesson plan. Research on the effectiveness of differentiation shows this method benefits a wide range of students, from those with learning disabilities to those who are considered high ability.

Differentiating instruction may mean teaching the same material to all students using a variety of instructional strategies, or it may require the teacher to deliver lessons at varying levels of difficulty based on the ability of each student.

Teachers who practice differentiation in the classroom may:

- Design lessons based on students' learning styles.
- Group students by shared interest, topic, or ability for assignments.
- Assess students' learning using formative assessment.

- Manage the classroom to create a safe and supportive environment.
- Continually assess and adjust lesson content to meet students' needs.

History of differentiated instruction

The roots of differentiated instruction go all the way back to the days of the one-room schoolhouse, where one teacher had students of all ages in one classroom. As the educational system transitioned to grading schools, it was assumed that children of the same age learned similarly. However, in 1912, achievement tests were introduced, and the scores revealed the gaps in student's abilities within grade levels.

In 1975, Congress passed the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), ensuring that children with disabilities had equal access to public education. To reach this student population, many educators used differentiated instruction strategies. Then came the passage of [No Child Left Behind](#) in 2000, which further encouraged differentiated and skill-based instruction - and that's because it works.

Four ways to differentiate instruction

According to Tomlinson, teachers can differentiate instruction through four ways: 1) content, 2) process, 3) product, and 4) learning environment.

1. Content

As you already know, fundamental lesson content should cover the standards of learning set by the school district or state educational standards. But some students in your class may be completely unfamiliar with the concepts in a lesson, some students may have partial mastery, and some students may already be familiar with the content before the lesson begins.

What you could do is differentiate the content by designing activities for groups of students that cover various levels of

[Bloom's Taxonomy](#) (a classification of levels of intellectual behavior going from lower-order thinking skills to higher-order thinking skills). The six levels are: remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating.

Students who are unfamiliar with a lesson could be required to complete tasks on the lower levels: remembering and understanding. Students with some mastery could be asked to apply and analyze the content, and students who have high levels of mastery could be asked to complete tasks in the areas of evaluating and creating.

Examples of differentiating activities:

- Match vocabulary words to definitions.
- Read a passage of text and answer related questions.
- Think of a situation that happened to a character in the story and a different outcome.
- Differentiate fact from opinion in the story.
- Identify an author's position and provide evidence to support this viewpoint.
- Create a PowerPoint presentation summarizing the lesson.

2. Process

Each student has a preferred learning style, and successful differentiation includes delivering the material to each style: visual, auditory and kinesthetic, and through words. This process-related method also addresses the fact that not all students require the same amount of support from the teacher, and students could choose to work in pairs, small groups, or individually. In addition, while some students may benefit from one-on-one interaction with you or the classroom aide, others may be able to progress by themselves. Teachers can enhance student learning by offering support based on individual needs.

Examples of differentiating the process:

- Provide textbooks for visual and word learners.
- Allow auditory learners to listen to audio books.
- Give kinesthetic learners the opportunity to complete an interactive assignment online.

3. Product

The product is what the student creates at the end of the lesson to demonstrate the mastery of the content. This can be in the form of tests, projects, reports, or other activities. You could assign students to complete activities that show mastery of an educational concept in a way the student prefers, based on learning style.

Examples of differentiating the product:

- Read and write learners write a book report.
- Visual learners create a graphic organizer of the story.
- Auditory learners give an oral report.
- Kinesthetic learners build a diorama illustrating the story.

4. Learning environment

The conditions for optimal learning include both physical and psychological elements. A flexible classroom layout is key, incorporating various types of furniture and arrangements to support both individual and group work. Psychologically speaking, teachers should use classroom management techniques that support a safe and supportive learning environment.

Examples of differentiating the environment:

- Break some students into reading groups to discuss the assignment.

- Allow students to read individually if preferred.
- Create quiet spaces where there are no distractions.

Pros and cons of differentiated instruction

The benefits of differentiation in the classroom are often accompanied by the drawback of an ever-increasing workload.

Pros

- Research shows differentiated instruction is effective for high-ability students as well as students with mild to severe disabilities.
- When students are given more options on how they can learn material, they take on more responsibility for their own learning.
- Students appear to be more engaged in learning, and there are reportedly fewer discipline problems in classrooms where teachers provide differentiated lessons.

Cons

- Differentiated instruction requires more work during lesson planning, and many teachers struggle to find the extra time in their schedule.
- The learning curve can be steep and some schools lack professional development resources. It's understandable that differentiated learning would seem overwhelming when you first start out. How can you teach the same concepts to students who work at different levels? However, once you get systems in place, you can move forward with confidence and your students can know their educational needs are being met.

References:

1. Westman, L. (2020, May). Why we need differentiation now more than ever. *Education Update*, 62(5).
2. What is Differentiated Instruction? Examples of How to Differentiate Instruction in the Classroom by Cathy Weselby
3. Nematova Zebo Tursunboevna, Tursunboeva Munisa To'lqin qizi. (2022). DIFFERENTIATED LESSON PLANS FOR STUDENTS AT DIFFERENT LEARNING LEVELS. *EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH*, 2(11), 1055–1059. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7251143>
4. What Differentiated Instruction Really Means. Lisa Westman
5. Tursunbaevna, N. Z. . (2022). Types of Interactive Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages in Higher Education Institutions. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 151–155. Retrieved from <https://www.grnjournals.us/index.php/ajshr/article/view/1560>
6. Nematova, Z. (2022). ADVANTAGES OF USING VIDEOS IN ENGLISH LESSONS.
7. Tursunboevna, N. Z., & Asomiddinovich, A. S. (2022). FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING.
8. Нематова, З. Т., & Хакимова, М. А. (2020). Songs in teaching English to young second language learners. *Молодой ученый*, (50), 497-499.
9. Tursunboevna, N. Z. (2022). Various types of assessment in language teaching and learning. *Eurasian journal of social sciences, philosophy and culture*, 2(3), 140-145.
10. Nematova, Z. T. (2019). THE USAGE OF SUGGESTOPEDIA FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND INCREASE SPEECH ACTIVITY. *Новый день в медицине*, (3), 21-24.